

CONSOLIDATION CONDITIONS FOR FLEXIBLE TOWPREG

G. Hudgins*, B. Love** and J. Muzzy***
Composites Manufacturing Research Program
*Engineering Science and Mechanics
**Materials Science and Engineering
***Chemical Engineering
Georgia Institute of Technology
Atlanta, Georgia 30332

ABSTRACT

Flexible towpreg can be produced from solid polymers, like thermoplastics, by powder fusion coating. This flexibility is due to the unconsolidated texture of the coated tows, which raises a concern regarding what conditions are required to make a consolidated structure from this towpreg. For unidirectional carbon fiber composites with matrices comprised of epoxy, nylon 6, nylon 11, and polypropylene relatively low time, temperature and pressure conditions have been explored. The peak temperatures and pressures studied ranged from 150 to 260°C and from 0.35 to 0.87 GPa. The times at peak conditions ranged from 5 to 30 minutes. The laminate flexural properties were generally consistent with the rule of mixtures. However, some polypropylene samples exhibited an inordinately high flexural modulus. Improved fiber wetting is needed for the polypropylene laminates.

1. INTRODUCTION

Prepregs based on solid polymers, such as thermoplastics, are rigid if the prepreg is fully consolidated. By focusing on coating individual fibers without consolidating the bundle of filaments comprising the tow or roving, it is possible to produce a flexible towpreg. This flexible towpreg is well suited for braiding and weaving flexible preforms (1,2,3) which can be molded into composite structures. Since this flexible towpreg is a new material form it is necessary to determine minimum molding conditions which will lead to acceptable structures. To explore this realm unidirectional laminates have been prepared from carbon fiber reinforced epoxy, nylon 6, nylon 11, and polypropylene. The molding conditions explored do not necessarily represent the minimum possible conditions; however, the focus is on short times, low pressure and low temperature.

The flexible towpregs were produced by a unique powder fusion coating process (4). A schematic diagram of the powder fusion coating process is shown in Figure 1. The tow is spread by an air banding jet to expose all the fibers. Electrostatically charged powder is deposited on the grounded tow. Then the powder is melted onto the fibers in an oven. The polymer solidifies before the towpreg is gathered in and wound on a bobbin. The resulting tow is partially wetted by the polymer but is far from being consolidated. Consequently, a unique flexible towpreg is obtained (5).

2. EXPERIMENTAL

The towpregs were prepared by Custom Composite Materials, Inc. (CCMI)(6). The carbon fiber used

Figure 1. Electrostatically Charged Powder Coating Line

in this study is 12,000 filament Celion G30-500 obtained from BASF and TOHO. Unsized fiber was used to facilitate spreading. The laminates were made at CCMi by winding the towpreg on a drum, seam welding the towpreg plies, laying up the plies in a graphite mold, heating the plies in the mold in a preheated press, applying a consolidation pressure for a specified time, and cooling the mold and laminate in a cold press at the same pressure (7).

Flexural testing was performed in accord with ASTM D 790 on 0° and 90° samples. For the transverse flexural tests a nominal span to depth ratio of 16 was used and testing was conducted at a crosshead speed of one mm/min. Fourpoint bending was used for the axial flexural testing with a nominal span to depth ratio of 32 and a crosshead speed of 5 mm/min. A rubber pad was used under the loading noses to minimize bearing load failure. A linear variable capacitance gauge was used to monitor the specimen deflection. Tensile and compressive testing was performed on a MTS Model 810 testing machine. A MTS biaxial extensometer was used to measure the strain.

3. BASELINE RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This portion of this study has been reported by CCMi (7). Table 1 presents baseline results for conservative consolidation conditions which were expected to lead to well consolidated laminates. Based on the laminate densities and fiber contents all the laminates had less than 2 percent void content. The epoxy, nylon 6 and nylon 11 samples exhibit relatively similar properties whereas the polypropylene laminate is unusual. The rule of mixtures can be used as a rough guideline. The approximate modulus and strength of Celion G30-500 are 210 GPa (30 msi) and 3,500 MPa (500 ksi) respectively. At 55 volume percent a G30-500 fiber unidirectional laminate is expected to have a tensile modulus close to 120 GPa and a tensile strength close to 1,950 MPa. In flexure some deviation from these tensile values is expected. What is not expected is a flexural modulus which greatly exceeds this rule of mixtures estimate, as reported for the polypropylene laminate. This high modulus is particularly surprising considering the low transverse flexural properties for this polypropylene laminate, indicating poor interfacial adhesion between the polymer and fiber. This polypropylene laminate requires further examination.

The epoxy, nylon 6 and nylon 11 samples all have a 0° modulus close to 120 GPa, in accord with the rule of mixtures estimate based on tensile properties. The transverse moduli for these three laminates is consistent with a simple equal stress model in both the fibers and matrix. The transverse moduli are all slightly higher than the neat resin moduli, which is typical of a filled polymer. The transverse modulus for the polypropylene laminate is reasonable based on the greater flexibility of polypropylene compared to epoxy and nylon 6.

The axial flexural strengths of the epoxy and nylon 6 samples are consistent with a rule of mixtures model. The axial flexural strengths of the nylon 11 and polypropylene laminates are low based on this standard. This low strength may reflect lower compressive properties. The transverse strengths of all

the laminates exceed the expected flexural strengths of the neat resins, indicating some interfacial adhesion. The epoxy, nylon 6 and nylon 11 samples all exceed the transverse strength of 75 MPa reported by Madhukar and Drzal for a well adhered carbon fiber/epoxy laminate with more than 60 volume percent fiber (8). Thus, these three laminates appear to be particularly well wet out with good interfacial strength. Based on this initial screening it would appear that milder molding conditions can be considered for all the materials except polypropylene. The interfacial adhesion in the polypropylene laminate appears to need improvement.

Table 1

Unidirectional Carbon Fiber Laminates from Flexible Towpreg (7)
(55 vol. % unsized Celion G30-500 12,000 filament tow)

Matrix:	Epoxy	Nylon 6*	Nylon 11*	Polypropylene
Supplier	Morton	Allied Signal	Atochem	Aristech
Particle Size, microns	20-30	40-50	20-40	80-200
Molding				
Peak Temperature, °C	150	260	230	230
Peak Pressure, kPa	700	870	870	870
Time @ Peak, min.	30	15	15	15
Flexural Properties				
0° Strength, MPa	1,700	1,980	1,260	1,130
90° Strength, MPa	100	153	137	26
0° Modulus, GPa	118	124	125	166
90° Modulus, GPa	8.7	10	7.4	5.0

* Dried 8 hours at 82°C before testing

4. VARIATIONS IN NYLON PROCESSING CONDITIONS

This phase of this study is still in progress. CCMi has reported some preliminary results for nylon 6 and 11 (7). For nylon 6 the pressure was not varied from 870 kPa; but, the temperature was lowered to 235 °C and the time at peak conditions was lowered to 5 minutes. The transverse strength still exceeded 100 MPa. In the case of nylon 11 the time at peak conditions was not changed from 15 minutes; but, the temperature was lowered to 218 °C and the pressure was lowered to 350 kPa. The transverse flexural strength did not drop below 120 GPa. Additional samples are needed to define the minimum bounds.

5. EXAMINATION OF POLYPROPYLENE LAMINATES

The polypropylene used in this study is a copolymer containing maleic anhydride. The anhydride groups should improve the adhesion to carbon fiber. The SEM micrograph shown in Figure 2 is from a transverse fracture surface. Matrix tearing from the fiber surface is apparent, which suggests good adhesion. The fracture surfaces from the axial flexure tests is difficult to examine since these samples delaminated close to the neutral plane. The other three laminates failed by fiber failure in tension followed by transverse cracking. Figure 3 is a polished section across this longitudinal crack. Bare fibers are clearly evident. In other locations fiber pull out was detected. It is apparent that the

Figure 2. SEM of Transverse Fracture Surface of Polypropylene Laminate.

Figure 3. SEM of Polished Surface Across a Longitudinal Delamination in an Axial Flexure Test of a Polypropylene Laminate.

polypropylene did not wet all the fibers. This poor wetting may be due to the much larger particle size used in powder coating with polypropylene. Unfortunately, it is difficult to produce much finer polypropylene powder. Considering this evidence of dry fiber and the low transverse flexural strength, it is even more surprising that the axial flexural modulus of the polypropylene laminate is so high based on elementary beam theory.

Tensile testing was performed on polypropylene laminates to check on the high apparent flexural modulus. Tensile tests were conducted on four samples according to ASTM D 3039 at a stroke rate of 2 mm/min. The average tensile modulus was 121 GPa. Tensile failure was not achieved because the samples slipped between the grips. Compression tests were also conducted on these samples since they were not damaged in tension. The stroke rate for the compression tests was 0.5 mm/min and the strain data was again collected with the extensometer. The compression tests were terminated upon the first visible sign of sample buckling. Compressive modulus values were calculated using stress and strain data well before the onset of buckling. The average compressive modulus was 87 GPa, significantly lower than the tensile modulus.

It is expected that the flexural modulus will not exceed the tensile modulus in most materials. If the tensile and compressive moduli of a material are different then the flexural modulus should fall between these two moduli. Therefore, a set of relations was developed based on first principles of beam mechanics in order to evaluate the unusual response observed in these polypropylene laminates. The description of beam kinematics applied to a linear material as presented by Wempner was followed (9). The resulting stress-strain relation is

$$S_{xx} = E(\epsilon_x - \kappa y) \quad (1)$$

where κ is the beam curvature and ϵ_0 is the axial strain along the reference plane. This expression for stress was substituted into the equilibrium equations for an arbitrary beam cross-section. The equilibrium equations were applied in the following manner to account for the nonhomogeneous material behavior: (a) The sum of the axial forces was set equal to zero (Equation 2) and (b) the internal moment was balanced with the external moment (Equation 4).

$$\int S_{xx} dA = \int E (\epsilon_0 - \kappa y) dA = 0 \quad (2)$$

$$\int_a^0 w E_T (\epsilon_0 - \kappa y) y dy - \int_0^b w E_C (\epsilon_0 - \kappa y) dy = 0 \quad (3)$$

$$M = - \int y S_{xx} dA = - \int_a^0 w E_T (\epsilon_0 - \kappa y) y dy - \int_0^b w E_C (\epsilon_0 - \kappa y) y dy \quad (4)$$

M is the external moment, w is the width of the specimen, a is the distance from the reference plane to the tensile surface, and b is the distance to the compressive surface. Integrating Equations 3 and 4 leads to Equations 5 and 6.

$$E_T a \epsilon_0 + E_C b \epsilon_0 + (E_T a^2 \kappa) / 2 - (E_C b^2 \kappa) / 2 = 0 \quad (5)$$

$$M = w E_T (\epsilon_0 a^2 / 2 - \kappa (-a)^3 / 3) - w E_C (\epsilon_0 b^2 / 2 - \kappa b^3 / 3) \quad (6)$$

These last two equations can be solved by selecting an arbitrary plane to obtain a and b for a sample of a given thickness. Next the moment, tensile modulus and compressive modulus can be substituted into these equations to solve for the curvature and axial strain. By setting the stress equal to zero the neutral axis can be found from Equation 1. Based on the tensile and compressive moduli reported above for the polypropylene laminate, 121 and 87 GPa, the neutral axis shifts about 8 percent from the geometric center plane towards the tensile side. The flexural modulus can be estimated from the following relationship:

$$E_f = M / (\kappa I) \quad (7)$$

where E_f is the flexural modulus and I is the moment of inertia. Based on Equation 7 the flexural modulus should be 102 GPa. This value is between the measured tensile and compressive moduli but well below the 166 GPa reported in Table 1. This analysis of the mechanics does not provide an explanation for the high apparent flexural modulus obtained experimentally.

An survey was made to see whether flexural moduli well above the tensile moduli are found in other unidirectional thermoplastic composites. Table 2 presents some representative results (10). Except for

Table 2
Unidirectional Thermoplastic Composites (10)

	Nylon 6	Polypropylene	PPS	PEEK
Fiber	Glass	Glass	Carbon	Carbon
Wt. % Fiber	50	65	NA*	NA*
Tensile Modulus, GPa	29	26	117	174
Flexural Modulus, GPa	24	18	131	131

* Not Available

the PPS laminate the tensile modulus exceeds the compressive modulus. Even in this case the increase in flexural modulus is small. The pattern shown in Table 2 is quite common; therefore, existing experimental results do not provide a basis for explaining the high flexural modulus obtained in this work.

6. CONCLUSIONS

By powder fusion coating it has been possible to make quality laminates at moderate consolidation conditions. In particular, nylon 6 and nylon 11 unidirectional laminates containing 55 volume percent carbon fiber were well consolidated using a peak pressure below 700 kPa and a peak temperature just 35 °C above their melting points for a peak time of 15 minutes. Lower peak processing conditions are feasible. An epoxy was well consolidated at this pressure. It's peak temperature, 150 °C, and hold time, 30 minutes, were based on the cure kinetics for this epoxy. Different consolidation and cure conditions for the epoxy laminates have not been explored.

Further work is required in making and evaluating polypropylene laminates. A progress report on this program will be given at the conference.

References

1. Muzzy, J., Varughese, B., and Yang, P., *Flexible Towpreg by Powder Fusion Coating of Filaments*, SPE ANTEC, Vol. 36, pp. 1385-1390, 1990.
2. Ramasamy, A., Muzzy, J., and Wang, Y., *Characterization of Flexible Towpreg for Textile Processing*, ICCM-9, this issue, 1993.
3. Ramasamy, A., PhD Thesis, Georgia Institute of Technology, Atlanta, GA (in preparation).
4. Muzzy, J., and Varughese, B., *Flexible Multiply Towpreg and Method of Production Therefor*, US Patent 5,094,883, 1992.
5. Muzzy, J., and Varughese, B., *Flexible Multiply Towpreg*, US Patent 5,171,630, 1992.
6. Custom Composite Materials, Inc., 2801 Bankers Industrial Dr., Atlanta, GA 30360.
7. Holty, D., Greene, T., Carpenter, C., and Davies, R., *Variables Affecting the Physical Properties of Consolidated Flexible Powder-Coated Towpregs*, Int'l SAMPE Symposium, Vol. 38, in press, 1993.
8. Madhukar, M., and Drzal, L., *Fiber-Matrix Adhesion and Its Effect on Composite Mechanical Properties: II. Longitudinal (0°) and Transverse (90°) Tensile and Flexure Behavior of Graphite/Epoxy Composites*, J. of Composite Materials, Vol. 25, pp. 958-991, 1991.
9. Wempner, G., *Mechanics of Solids with Applications to Thin Bodies*, Sijthoff and Noordhoff, Rockville, MD., 1981.
10. Raghupathi, N., *Long Fiber Thermoplastic Composites*, Mallick, P., and Newman, S., Editors, *Composite Materials Technology*, Hanser, Munich, 1990.